

Expressing a Conserved Quantity in Terms of a Derivative to Create a Variational Principle in Physics

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In this note we wish to examine two cases in which variational principles seem to follow from expressing conserved quantities in terms of derivatives. Given conservation in a system, conserved quantities may be expressed in terms of “derivatives” which add to zero creating the variational principle. The first case is Fermat's Least Time Principle for light which is equivalent to conservation of momentum in the direction of an invariant spatial variable for two ray problems (reflection/refraction, reflection from a moving mirror). In the case of a particle with mass Maupertuis' principle for particles with rest mass (1) seems to behave in the same manner. In fact, one may create two different variational principles. The first deals with using d/dx acting on $\sqrt{xx+yy}$ to create $\sin(\theta)$ which appears in $(p_x) = p \sin(\theta)$ if θ is measured from the y axis. The second approach is more direct and involves multiply (p_x) by x i.e. ultimately creating $A = -Et + (p_x)x + (p_y)y + (p_z)z$.

In a Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) gas this same idea seems to appear again. One may use a variational principle i.e. maximize entropy with respect to the constraint $\sum_i e_i n(i) = E$ or use time reversal of an elastic collision i.e. $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$ and $n(e_1)n(e_2) = n(e_3)n(e_4)$. Taking \ln of the latter and equating to the former multiplied by a constant yields the MB distribution. Thus one associates $\ln(n(e_i))$ with $-e_i/T$ where e_i is a conserved quantity. From this conserved quantity one may mathematically create a variational principle i.e. the maximization of entropy. Like with $-Et + px$ one may associate $\ln(n(e_i))$ with $-e_i/T$ i.e. take conserved quantity and multiply it by the variable $n(e_i)$ so that $d/d n(e_i)$ returns e_i .

We argue that ultimately in Fermat's principle and that of an MB gas, one associates a function with a conserved quantity namely $p \sin(\theta) = p_x$ (conserved quantity) or $\ln(n(e_i)) = -e_i/T$ where e_i is part of a conservation equation.

As a result, it may seem as if there are two independent ways to obtain physical solutions for the same problem. For example in (2) it states that Snell's law may be obtained either using conservation of momentum in the x direction or Fermat's principle. For an MB gas one may maximize entropy subject to a constraint or use reaction balance. We argue that these approaches are not independent. Given a conserved quantity, one may mathematically create a corresponding variational principle at least in these two cases.

Fermat's Least Time Principle for Two Ray Light Problems

Fermat's least time principle for light is often applied to reflection (from moving or stationary mirrors) and refraction. The idea is to write an expression for time in terms of spatial variables i.e. x, y and then vary one of these. The variable which is varied i.e. x which is an invariant spatial variable is not chosen by accident because this variable is associated with conservation of momentum in that direction i.e. (p_x) . Y is not varied because the mirror or medium surface lies along the x axis at a fixed y point e.g. $y=0$. In other words the mirror position is a constraint in the system which is not changed. This forces one to vary the variable which is not linked with

any constraint namely x . As a result one writes $t = \text{distance} / \text{speed}$ for each ray and takes $d/dx (t_1 + t_2) = 0$. One may see that this is equivalent to a conservation law i.e.:

$$dt_1/dx = -dt_2/dx \quad ((1))$$

One may note the minus sign in ((1)), but t_1 depends on x and t_2 on $L-x$ which takes care of this minus. In particular for refraction:

$$t_1 = n_1/c \sqrt{xx + YY} \quad \text{and} \quad t_2 = n_2/c \sqrt{(L-x)(L-x) + YY} \quad ((2))$$

Taking d/dx of either t_1 or t_2 immediately leads to a $\sin(\theta_1)$ or $\sin(\theta_2)$ form. This form, however, is directly linked to the $\sin(\theta_1)$ and $\sin(\theta_2)$ in the conservation of momentum in the x direction i.e.

$$p_1 \sin(\theta_1) = p_2 \sin(\theta_2) \quad ((3)) \quad \text{where} \quad p_1 = n_1 p \quad \text{and} \quad p_2 = n_2 p \quad \text{with} \quad p \quad \text{being} \quad \text{momentum} \quad \text{in} \quad \text{a} \quad \text{vacuum.}$$

In particular, one may start with a conservation law based on invariance in a certain direction namely x and then create variational principles. In this case, one may create two variational principles.

Fermat's Principle and Variation of Time

Beginning with conservation of momentum in the x direction, namely ((3)), one may try to express $\sin(\theta_1)$ and $\sin(\theta_2)$ in terms of d/dx and then use $p_1 \sin(\theta_1) - p_2 \sin(\theta_2) = 0$ to create a variational principle.

$$d/dx \sqrt{xx + yy} = x / \sqrt{xx + yy} = \sin(\theta_1) \quad \text{and} \quad d/dx \sqrt{(L-x)(L-x) + yy} = -\sin(\theta_2) \quad ((4))$$

Thus the length of ray may be used in a variational principle, but it needs to be multiplied by n_1 or n_2 because $p_1 = n_1 p$ and $p_2 = n_2 p$ where p is the momentum of light in a vacuum because $E = pc$ and E remains constant in refraction.

Given that light speed is c/n_1 and c/n_2 respectively and that distance = speed* time, one may create a variation of time principle i.e. Fermat's principle, but this is not the only variational principle one may create.

We stress that a Fermat's least time principle is equivalent to conservation of momentum in the x direction for mirrors/media with surfaces in the x direction because a variational principle creates the sense that the system may somehow test different paths and then choose the correct one when in fact the principle is based on a conserved quantity which simply does not change. Thus (p_x) does not change, but (p_y) does at the mirror/medium surface. Thus one need not think in terms of different paths being tested and the minimum one chosen.

-Et+px Variational Principle

Conservation of momentum in the x direction leads to another variational type principle which is more direct. If (px) is the conserved quantity then simply multiplying by x gives a quantity whose d/dx derivative yields the conserved quantity. Thus one may create the function:

$$A = -Et + (px)x + (py)y + (pz)z \quad ((5))$$

This is a Lorentz invariant, but one sees that $dA/dx = px$ i.e. the conserved quantity. A happens to be both the relativistic and nonrelativistic classical action for a free particle written with $v=x/t$ and x and t considered independent. This form is also linked to quantum mechanics.

In such a case, one may consider the x direction and consider a starting point of $x=0$ and an ending one of $x=L$. Then:

$(px)x + px(L-x) = (px)L$ so that all information about x disappears. One may also take the derivative of this expression with respect to x to obtain 0.

Maupertuis' Variational Principle for Particles with Rest Mass

In (1) Maupertuis' variational principle is applied to particles with rest mass to mimic the refraction problem. In this case a particle with fixed energy moves from a region with a constant potential V_1 into one with a constant potential V_2 such that the interface is along the x axis at $y=b$. Thus $y=b$ is a constraint and so x is again the free variable used in the variation. Newton's law already dictates that momentum in the x direction must be conserved because there is no nonzero dV/dx in this direction. Thus the x variable is invariant.

In (1) Maupertuis' variational principle is formulated as:

$$\Delta \int_{(t_a, t_b)} dt \sum (i) p(i) dq(i)/dt \quad ((6))$$

For the two constant potential regions one has: $mv_1v_1 \Delta t_1 + mv_2v_2 \Delta t_2$

The problem is now very similar to a Fermat's refraction one because:

$$\Delta t_1 = d/dx \sqrt{(x^2 + y^2)} / v_1 \quad \text{and} \quad \Delta t_2 = d/dx \sqrt{[(L-x)(L-x) + y^2]} / v_2 \quad ((7))$$

This again leads to a conservation of momentum in the x direction. Using Newton's law, however, one may start with conservation of momentum i.e.

$$p_1 \sin(\theta_1) = p_2 \sin(\theta_2) \quad ((8))$$

and write $\sin(\theta)$ in terms of d/dx i.e. $d/dx \sqrt{(x^2+y^2)}$ or $d/dx \sqrt{[(L-x)(L-x) + y^2]}$ ((9))

Thus ((8)) again can be changed into two variational principles, namely one based on ((9)) and the other on $-Et+px$.

Interestingly $-Et+px$ is the same form for light and a particle with rest mass.

Maximization of Entropy in a Maxwell-Boltzmann Gas

The idea of conserved quantity being transformed into a variational principle is not limited to Fermat's or Maupertuis' principles. It seems it appears in the case of a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas (MB). A variational approach often seems to be the preferred one, namely the maximization of entropy with respect to a constraint on energy i.e.

$$E = \sum_i n(e_i) e_i \quad \text{and} \quad S \text{ is proportional to } \ln\left\{ \frac{N!}{\prod_i n(e_i)!} \right\} \quad ((10))$$

Here entropy is essentially \ln of a number of arrangements where $n(e_i)$ is the number of particles with energy e_i . Then:

$$\frac{d}{d n(e_i)} \left\{ -n(e_i) \ln(n(e_i)) + B e_i n(e_i) \right\} = 0 \quad \text{or} \quad n(e_i) \text{ proportional to } \exp(-e_i/T) \quad ((11))$$

where Stirling's approximation has been used and $B = \text{constant} = 1/\text{Temperature}$. This approach leads one to think in terms of maximizing arrangements, but we argue in the next section that one may "create" this variational principle from a physical interaction/conservation scenario. Like with Fermat's principle of least time we suggest one should be a little careful about the system knowing about minimum time or a maximum number of arrangements as these variational procedures follow from mathematical manipulations of physical conservation laws.

Reaction Balance in a Maxwell-Boltzmann Gas

The Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution may be derived directly from imposing a time reversal reaction balance on elastic two body collisions. In this case conservation is linked to single particle kinetic energy.

$$E_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4 \quad \text{and} \quad n(e_1) n(e_2) = n(e_3) n(e_4) \quad ((12))$$

$$\text{Taking } \ln \text{ of the latter and equating: } \ln(n(e_i)) = -e_i/T \quad \text{yields } n(e_i) \text{ proportional to } \exp(-e_i/T) \quad ((13))$$

This approach seems to be based directly on the interactions in the system, namely two body elastic ones and the idea that the probability for an interaction is $n(e_1)n(e_2)$. It also introduces the idea of information invariance, namely that any e_i+e_j which equals E is on the same footing. Although the $n(e_i)$'s are not on the same footing, their products $n(e_i)n(e_j)$ are. Thus there is a

loss of information in the system or a kind of invariance. This is similar to the loss of x information in Fermat's principle i.e $x + (L-x) = L$ so x disappears.

In the reaction balance approach the conserved quantity e_i is associated with $\ln(n(e_i))$ through:

$$\ln(n(e_i)) = -e_i/T \quad ((14))$$

The easiest way to change ((14)) into a derivatives of $n(e_i)$ (like with $-Et+px$) is to multiply by $n(e_i)$ Then:

$$d/d n(e_i) \quad n(e_i) \ln(n(e_i)) = - d/d n(e_i) \quad e_i n(e_i) / T \quad ((15))$$

This approach works because $d/dn(e_i) \quad n(e_i) \ln(n(e_i)) = n(e_i) + \text{constant}$ with the constant not upsetting the process.

Thus starting with reaction balance one may "create" a variational form, namely ((15)).

Using Stirling's approximation $\ln(n!) \approx n \ln(n) - n$ and dropping n leads to the "arrangements" picture for large n values. We suggest, however, that this variational approach follows directly from reaction balance. It should be noted that reaction balance also assumes large n .

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that some variational principles in physics such as Fermat's least time principle for light, Maupertuis' principle for particles with rest mass and maximization of entropy subject to the constraint of fixed energy for a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas may be obtained through mathematically transforming direct conservation laws. The variational principles are interesting, but they give a sense of the system somehow sensing a path of minimum time or a maximum number of arrangements when perhaps a more direct conservation law may account for this. For example, for Fermat's or Maupertuis' principle, conservation of momentum in the direction of an invariant spatial variable is direct. A variable is invariant if there is no constraint linked with it suggesting no force in that direction. For example, a mirror or medium surface may lie along the x axis at $y=0$. $y=0$ is a constraint and x is an invariant variable leading to conservation of (px) .

In the case of reaction balance which deals directly with physical interactions in a system which are responsible for equilibrium, conservation of energy exists. One may link $\ln(n(e_i))$ to e_i and then create a variational principle, namely the maximization of entropy subject to constant energy from this idea by multiplying by $n(e_i)$ and then taking the derivative $d/dn(e_i)$.

Thus we suggest that a link between a variational principle and a conservation one exists in two very different areas of physics and may exist in others.

References

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